

DYNAMIC EFFECTS OF BLACK TAX AND FOREIGN EXCHANGE RESERVES ON EXCHANGE RATE IN NIGERIA: EVIDENCE OF A MODERATING ROLE USING THE GMM APPROACH.

¹Toyin Waliu Otapo, ^{*2}Paul Obogo Ushie, ³Wale Henry Agbaje (Ph.D.), ⁴James Adeniyi Demehin and ⁵Foluso Ololade Oluwole

^{1,2,4,5}Department of Finance, Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba-Akoko, Ondo State, Nigeria

³Department of Accounting, Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba-Akoko, Ondo State, Nigeria

ORCID No: *0000-0002-9128-8526

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Abstract: The increasing wave of relocation by successful black professionals from developing countries to more developed economies in search of better economic opportunities has led to increased remittance back home to support friends and extended families. The effect of these remittances, otherwise called the black tax, on the exchange rate, and its moderating effect on the stabilization role of the reserve on the exchange rate are yet to be fully established in the literature. This study therefore tested the isolated effect of the black tax on exchange rate, the effect of reserve on exchange rate and the moderating effect of black tax on the stabilization role of reserve on exchange rate in Nigeria.

The study's data represent Nigeria economic data from 1981 to 2024, obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin. The study modelled the exchange rate as dependent on reserves, current transfer (black tax), the interaction variable between reserve and current transfer, and control variables of number of commercial bank branches (financial inclusion), money supply, Gross Domestic product, interest rate and trade balance.

Results indicate that increases in reserve (-176.9671, P=0.2439) money supply (-345.191, P=0.2764) and trade balance (-1.00E-12, P=0.8444) are associated with appreciation of the Naira, while increases in black tax (1.36E-11, P=0.1018), GDP (317.3012, P=0.1495), number of commercial bank branches (10.16075, P=0.8331) and interest rate (3.373, P=0.78) are associated with depreciation of the naira. When isolated, an increase in black tax depreciates the Naira. However, its moderating role strengthens the stabilizing effect of the reserve on exchange rate (-9.07E-12). However, this moderating effect is not significant (0.1822 at 10%,) just like all other exogenous variables.

The study recommended the encouragement of export earnings from oil and non-oil sources, an integrated management of diaspora remittances and reserves, reduction in transaction costs of diaspora remittances, investment in small and medium scale enterprises and promotion of digital financial services.

Keywords: Black Tax, GMM, Foreign Exchange Reserve, Moderating Role, Exchange Rate.

1. INTRODUCTION

Developing economies including African countries are characterized by social and economic inequality, citizens are differently endowed and economic opportunities differ among the working class, the poor and unconnected

being worse off, as such, the skilled and well-educated professionals increasingly travel abroad to seek for better economic opportunities. However, these few successful black professionals that are fortunate to travel to foreign developed countries are obliged to provide financial support to their extended families back home (Bolma & Adeyemi, 2024; Carpenter & Phaswana, 2021). This unrequited financial support to extended family is called black tax. Manyike (2019) similarly defined black tax as the financial support extended to family members by young black professionals who are more successful within their family structures, other less fortunate members of the nuclear and extended family look forward to these few black professionals to meet their financial needs (Powell & Du Plessis, 2024). Some authors perceive black tax as a financial burden undertaken to support extended family members (Magubane, 2017; Mangoma & Wilson-Prangley, 2019). It is considered as an unpleasant and oppressive experience (Magubane, 2017; Sibiya, 2018) capable of impeding personal savings and investment drive leaving young professional to feel that their needs are less important while prioritizing extended family welfare (Mangoma & Wilson-Prangley, 2019;). On the contrary some researchers considered black tax as an instrument for reducing poverty among blacks, rather than being oppressive, it is considered as evidence of the collectivist element of African culture promoting community or family remittances (Sibiya, 2018).

Black tax or family remittances from family and friends living abroad is one of the sources of reserve accumulation aside positive trade balance, capital inflows, exchange rate rate policy, interest rate and revenue from the sale of natural resources. Foreign reserve which is otherwise called external reserve, international reserve or foreign exchange reserve (Osuji & Ebiringa, 2012) was defined by the International Monetary Fund (2007) as consisting of official public sector foreign assets that are readily available to and controlled by the monetary authorities, for the direct financing of payment imbalances and directly regulating the magnitude of such imbalances through intervention in the exchange markets to effect the currency exchange rate and/ or for other purposes. Economies of the world accumulate foreign reserve for different objectives which include: to possess a buffer stock used for smoothening output and consumption in times of crises and external shocks (Aizeman & Lee, 2007; Aizeman & Hutchison, 2010), to ensure market confidence and reduce sovereign borrowing cost (Alfaro & Kanczuk, 2009; Bianchi et al., 2013), to pursue an export led economic growth strategy (Dooley et al., 2003) or hold reserve due to economic fragility and shallow financial development (Cabellero et al. 2008; Obstfeld et al., 2010). The aforementioned are the motives sovereign nations accumulate foreign reserves and this behavior is noticed in both developed and developing countries. Theoretically, Changes in the foreign reserve have direct effect on the exchange rate of a country.

Exchange rate is defined as the amount of a domestic currency that exchange for a unit of a foreign currency or the amount of a foreign currency that exchange for a unit of a domestic currency, Osigwe and Uzonwanne (2015) defined exchange rate as the value of one country's currency in terms of another currency. Exchange rates are determined based on the exchange rate policy pursued in the country which can be fixed, floating or managed float. In fixed exchange rate regime, the government determines the exchange rate and maintains this rate through intervention in the exchange rate market while in the case of floating or flexible exchange rate regime, the rate is determined by the supply of and demand for foreign currency in the foreign exchange market. A managed float is an intermediate policy exhibiting government control and intervention but largely the rate is being determined by the forces of demand and supply. Supply sources of foreign currency include net current account (unrequited transfers, black tax/ remittances), capital inflows and receipts from exports while its demand sources include imports, profit repatriation, education and health tourism and so on. When the exchange rate reduces, the domestic currency is said to appreciate and when it increases it depreciates.

The exchange rate of one dollar to the naira was largely stable between 1981 and 1985 at 0.6 and 0.8 respectively, a significant increase in the exchange rate was noticed in 1986 at 2.02 due to the advent of the structural

adjustment programme and the introduction of the managed float, thereafter a steady increase in the exchange rate characterized the Nigerian economy. The exchange rate was below N200 to one dollar as at 2015 but rose steadily to N645 in 2023. A significant increase in the exchange rate was noticed in 2024 where it increased by more than 200% of the previous year's figures. Similarly, the foreign reserve witnessed a steady increasing trajectory from 1981 to 2003 at \$2441 Million and \$746 million, this increased sharply to \$16955 million in 2004, and up till 2024 averaged \$37246 yearly with the highest recorded in 2008 at \$53000 Million.

The black tax measured by net current transfer or unrequited transfer was negative between 1981 and 1987. It however became positive from 1988 and rose steadily to N51548 million in 1995. A three hundred percent increase was noticed in 1996 from the previous year's figure at N194518 million and has increased yearly till 2004 recording a yearly average N203900 million. Another huge increase occurred in 2005 when net current transfer was almost N2billion and has consistently been above that figure up till 2024 when it recorded N35.5 billion. the financial inclusion measure of number of commercial banks branches and trade balance equally experienced increasing trajectory from 1981 till 2024. The Dollar exchange rate has a strong positive co movement with net current transfer (black tax) at 0.98 but a moderate positive co movement with reserves at 0.526, similarly, net current transfer moderately and positively co move with reserves at 0.529.

Between 1981 and 2024, the Nigerian economy witnessed a highly volatile trade balance but with a long run increase, current transfers (black tax) also exhibited a strong continuous growth, similarly, foreign reserves were fluctuating but generally rising. Exchange rate exhibited a persistent depreciation and the number of bank branches grew until 2017 after which there was a mild decline. The positive correlation between net current transfers and reserves suggests that the former increases the later contributing to reserve accumulation, however such increase in reserve is not proportional since reserve accumulation also depends on trade balance, capital flows exchange rate policy and oil revenue. The persistence of exchange rate depreciation may be due to high import demand, external debt obligation or structural economic reforms, relevant questions necessitating this research are: what is the influence of black tax (Current transfer) on exchange rate, what is the effect of reserves on exchange rate in Nigeria and what is the moderating role of black tax on the effect of reserves on exchange rate.

Reviewed works in their models did not include black tax as a moderating variable when testing the effect of reserve on exchange rate in addition, the theoretical link between reserve and exchange rate as mediated by black tax (net current account) needs to be empirically verified in Nigeria. This study will address these gaps and its result will inform the direction of government economic policies to achieve desired macro-economic objectives. Following this introduction, section 2 reviewed literature while section 3 contains the methodology, the discussion of findings is contained in section 4 while the study's conclusion and recommendations are contained in section 5.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual review

Exchange Rate

A country's exchange rate is the amount of the domestic currency that will exchange for a unit of a foreign currency (Krugman, et al. 2018) the rate is important in international trade macroeconomic stability and capital flows, exchange rate affects imports, exports, external reserves and net foreign investment (Mishkin, 2019; Salvatore, 2019). Types of exchange rates include nominal exchange rate, real exchange rate, fixed exchange rate and floating exchange rates. The nominal exchange rate is the price of one currency relative to another while the real exchange is obtained when the nominal rate is adjusted for inflation differentials between the countries. Fixed exchange rates are largely determined arbitrarily by the government and defended by it through active intervention

in the exchange market conversely, the flexible exchange rate is determined by the interplay of the supply of and demand for foreign currency, the price (rate) where the demand equals supply (equilibrium) is the exchange rate. Fluctuations in exchange rate is brought about by changes in interest rates, inflation, foreign reserves trade balance, and capital flows

Black tax

Black tax otherwise called remittances or family transfers is a socio economic construct that refers to the obligations on successful individuals to provide financial support to friends, communities and extended family members that are less privileged (Ratha, 2013; Adams & Page, 2005) . The privileged and successful black professionals who travel abroad and are economically successful are obliged to send money to extended family members back home, this is usually captured as remittances or current transfer in the balance of payment report. In Nigeria over the years, black tax has increasingly become an important component of external financial inflow, increased black tax remittance will increase foreign currency supply leading to increased foreign reserves thereby assisting to stabilize the exchange rate. Where, black tax remittance is used for consumption its economic impact will be limited, but where such remittances pass into savings channeled into investment its multiplier effect on the economy will be significant.

Foreign Reserves

Foreign reserves of a country is the stock of foreign currency, gold and special drawing rights used by the monetary authority to stabilize domestic currency, maintain confidence in the international debt market (Aizenman & lee, 2007), finance balance of payment deficits, and defend the economy against external shocks (Jeanne & Ranciere, 2011). The Nigerian economy is mono export relying heavily on proceeds of crude oil sales as source of foreign currency inflow, its reserves consequently fluctuate in response to changes in oil earnings, remittances and capital inflows. A large reserve improves the capacity of the monetary authority to stabilize the exchange rate fluctuations, however a dwindling reserve will elicit depreciation of the domestic currency.

Theoretical review

Theories of exchange rate determination include, the purchasing power parity (PPP), balance of payment (BOP), the monetary approach, the portfolio balance model and the interest rate parity. The purchasing power parity states that exchange rate equals the ratio of the prices of a basket of goods across countries, as the prices of the basket of goods changes, the exchange rate changes accordingly, therefore exchange rate between a domestic and foreign country is the price of the basket of goods in the domestic country divided by the price of the same basket of goods in the foreign country (Hakkio, 1984), in the balance of payment theory, exchange rates adjust to balance international transactions such that when foreign currency inflows are in the excess of its outflows (BOP surplus), domestic currency appreciates but it depreciates if the converse is the case (BOP deficit), this theory posits that the key drivers of exchange rate include exports, imports, capital flows remittances and foreign investment (Dornbusch, 1976; Edwards, 1989). In the monetary approach, exchange rate is determined by the interplay of money supply, interest rates and inflation. Where the money growth rate in a domestic country is high relative to other countries its exchange rates depreciate (Frankel,1976; Mussa, 1976). However, in the portfolio balance model, exchange rates are influenced by investors choices of domestic and foreign assets (Branson, 1977; Frankel, 1984), assets choices are shaped by investors risk perception, expected returns and interest rate differentials, when investors adjust their portfolios in response to changes in these factors, net capital flows change ultimately affecting exchange rate. Lastly, the interest parity model states that exchange rate is determined by the differentials in interest rate, higher domestic interest rate relative to foreign interest rate attracts more capital inflows leading to currency appreciation. The role of robust financial intermediation is germane in determining and regulating the

exogeneous variables in the above theories, an improving financial inclusion outlook is therefore equally important in the determination of exchange rate.

Empirical review

Reviewed empirical works concentrated on the effects of reserve accumulation on macro-economic measures, effect of economic development on reserve, causal relationship between reserve and economic indices and determination of the optimal reserve. Usman and Ibrahim (2010) investigated the impact of change in reserve on domestic investment, inflation rate and exchange rate using ordinary least square regression and the vector error correction model, the study concluded that reserve affects foreign direct investment and exchange rate but has no influence on domestic investment and inflation, Lubis (2022) similarly carried out a panel regression analyses investigating the effect of foreign reserve accumulation on export and foreign direct investment using ARDL/PMG, FMOLS and DOLS, the study also concluded that reserve has a significant and positive effect on export and foreign direct investment. On the contrary, some reviewed works established that reserve accumulation does not significantly influence economic growth, for instance, Nwafor (2017) considered external reserve as a solution to economic growth in Nigeria and concluded that foreign reserve has no significant positive influence on economic growth, likewise, Adeniji et al. (2025) also concluded that foreign reserve do not have a significant effect in driving economic growth in Nigeria.

Another group of reviewed work investigated the effect of economic indices on reserve accumulation, for instance, Alam and Hasan (2021) studied the impact of economic development on foreign reserve using the vector error correction model and granger causality test, the study concluded that economic growth and reserve accumulation have long term positive relationship, the granger causality test also confirm short and long-term relationships between the variables.

Evidence of the investigation of causal relationship between reserve accumulation and economic indices was also found in literature, Osigwe and Uzonwanne (2015) investigated the Granger causality among foreign reserve, exchange rate and foreign direct investment in Nigeria using the unit root and Johansen co integration tests, their study found a unidirectional causality flowing from exchange rate to foreign reserve, then from foreign direct investment to foreign reserve. Bi directional causality was established between foreign reserve and foreign direct investment at lag 3 and a unidirectional causality flowing from exchange rate to foreign direct investment at lags 1 and 3. Likewise, Kashif et al. (2024) investigated the causal relationship between Brazil's accumulated international reserve and economic growth using the Augmented Dickey Fuller unit root test, Zivot- Andrews unit root test, the Granger causality test and the Johansen's cointegration test, the study established a linear and non linear causality between foreign exchange reserves and economic growth. Lastly, researchers also attempted to determine the optimal amount of reserve that a country should hold, Tule et al. (2017) ascertained the optimal level of international reserve for Nigeria that is adequate to absorb shocks. Their study employed the generalized autoregressive conditional heteroscedasticity, VAR and normalized Johanssen cointegration test, positive relationships were established between the odds of default on sovereign debt and fiscal deficit to GDP ratio, between short term debt to reserve ratio and volatility in portfolio investment. The study further asserts that Nigeria needs \$32Billion to adequately absorb external shocks. There is a growing penchant among the educated youths in Nigeria to travel to developed countries in search of better economic opportunities, remittances of these successful professionals back home to financially support their family and friends has tremendously increased over time, empirically measuring the moderating effect of these black tax is necessary and will inform government fiscal and monetary policies to encourage or discourage it.

3. METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted by the study is ex post facto which is appropriate since the study's data are past economic indices obtained from secondary sources which are not open to manipulations. The study's data is Nigeria macro-economic data between 1981 and 2024 obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical bulletin. The generalized method of moment (GMM) method of regression was adopted to estimate the study's data.

Model Specification

The study's model is built on the combined theories of balance of payment, monetary approach and the portfolio balance approach.

The balance of payment theory modelled exchange rate (EXR) to depend on trade balance (TBL), Current transfer (CT) which proxied black tax and reserves (RES), that is

$$EXR = f(TBL, CT, RES) \dots\dots\dots 1$$

On the hand, the monetary approach opined that exchange rate depends on money supply (MS), gross domestic product (GDP), and reserves whose functional equation is therefore

$$EXR = f(MS, GDP, RES) \dots\dots\dots 2$$

While the portfolio balance modeled exchange rate to depend on reserves, interest rate (IR), and capital flow (CA) whose functional equation is

$$EXR = f(RES, INT, CA) \dots\dots\dots 3$$

When the three models are integrated and the control variable of financial Inclusion (FI, proxied by number of commercial bank branches NOB) added, the study's equation becomes

$$EXR = f(RES, CT, TBL, MS, GDP, INT, NOB) \dots\dots\dots 4$$

A focus of the study is to measure the moderating effect of black tax (CT) on the influence of reserve on exchange rate. This is captured by the variable (RES x CT) and the model becomes

$$EXR = f(RES, CT, (RES \times CT) TBL, MS, GDP, INT, NOB) \dots\dots\dots 5$$

The Generalized method of Moment (GMM) specification of the model becomes

$$EXR_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 RES_{stdt} + \beta_2 ihsCT_{ct} + \beta_3 (RES_{stdt} \times ihsCT_{ct}) + \beta_4 ihsTBL_{ct} + \beta_5 MS_{std} + \beta_6 GDP_{std} + \beta_7 INT_{std} + \beta_8 NOB + u \dots\dots\dots 6$$

Some of the variables (current transfer and trade balance) contain negative values, these are transformed using the Inverse Hyperbolic Sine (IHS) transformation and then centered to achieve uniform scale. HIS transformation is obtained thus

$HIS(X) = \log(X + \sqrt{X^2+1})$ and centering is obtained thus, $X_c = X - \text{mean}$. To achieve scale uniformity other variables are standardized i.e $X_{std} = (X - \text{mean}X) / (\text{Standard deviation of } X)$, however exchange rate is used at level without transformation (Wooldridge, 2013)

GMM is adopted in the study because of its peculiar advantages, it produces consistent result even when some of the regressors are endogenous, it can handle heteroscedasticity and serial correlation errors and can accommodate interaction terms obtained from both HIS transformed and standardized variables, lastly GMM is suitable for small samples (Hansen, 1982)

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Descriptive statistics

The descriptive statistics of the study's variables are contained in table 4.1

Table 4.1: Descriptive statistics

	EXR	GDP_STD	IHSCT_C	IHSTBL_C	INT_STD	MS_STD	NOB_STD	RES_STD	RESCT
Mean	158.7564	4.42E-08	-0.008523	-0.002841	-3.58E-07	9.14E-08	1.59E-07	1.12E-07	2.40E+13

Median	119.7685	-0.544683	2.25E+13	-8.48E+12	0.000381	-0.514001	-0.187859	-0.587450	1.62E+13
Maximum	1478.965	3.185030	6.10E+14	1.81E+14	2.783020	4.290068	1.377745	1.866451	6.95E+14
Minimum	0.610025	-0.719087	2.26E+13	-8.53E+12	-2.047779	-0.590486	-1.500054	-1.133218	3.67E+13
Std. Dev.	247.7464	1.000000	9.59E+13	2.87E+13	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000	1.05E+14
Skewness	3.724790	1.536455	6.063419	5.903993	0.362721	2.510905	0.107083	0.322383	6.060170
Kurtosis	19.67264	4.580196	39.00516	37.76988	3.579830	9.952023	1.395588	1.468950	39.20457
Jarque-Bera	611.3674	21.88962	2646.291	2472.018	1.581195	134.8402	4.803342	5.059703	2672.402
Probability	0.000000	0.000018	0.000000	0.000000	0.453574	0.000000	0.090567	0.079671	0.000000
Sum	6985.283	1.95E-06	-0.250000	-0.156250	-1.58E-05	4.02E-06	6.99E-06	4.94E-06	1.06E+15
Sum Sq. Dev.	2639265.	43.00000	3.96E+29	3.55E+28	43.00000	43.00000	42.99999	43.00002	4.76E+29
Observations	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44

Source: Authors computation 2026

The exchange rate with a standard deviation of 247.74 is highly volatile, positively skewed (3.72) and extremely leptokurtic (19.67), this confirms few extreme depreciation episodes and frequent extreme shocks and outliers in the Nigerian exchange rate, furthermore the exchange rate distribution is not normally distributed with a Jarque – Bera of 611.37 and a probability of zero. The Jaque Bera statistics for the independent variables are significant with GDP (21.88, P=0), current transfer (2646.29, P=0), trade balance (2472.018, P=0), money supply (134.84, P=0), and the interaction variable combining reserve and current transfer (2672.402, P=0) , consequently, the null hypothesis that the distribution are normally distributed is rejected (not normal). However, the Jarque Bera Statistics are not significant and distributions are therefore normal in the cases of interest rate (1.581, P= 0.45), number of commercial bank branches (4.80, P=0.09) and reserve (5.059, P=0.0796). Majority of the study’s variables exhibits high skewness, not normally distributed and high kurtosis which suggest the presence of outliers and non-linearity in the study’s data. However, the GMM method of estimation remain appropriate since it does not require normality assumption before it can be used. The mean and standard deviations of the standardized variables are close to zero and 1 respectively, this confirms that the variables are correctly normalized and scale comparability is ensured across all the variables.

Pairwise correlation

Table 4.2 below contains the correlation coefficients between pairs of the study’s variables

Table 4.2: pairwise correlation coefficient

	EXR	GDP_STD	IHSCT_C	IHSTBL_C	INT_STD	MS_STD	NOB_STD	RES_STD	RESCT
EXR	1.000000	0.881225	0.905671	0.863947	-0.128145	0.955526	0.557833	0.526519	0.804529
GDP_STD	0.881225	1.000000	0.629624	0.577619	-0.246999	0.968763	0.754687	0.683345	0.474468
IHSCT_C	0.905671	0.629624	1.000000	0.970951	-0.073674	0.784762	0.247855	0.256336	0.974642
IHSTBL_C	0.863947	0.577619	0.970951	1.000000	-0.051588	0.726367	0.302481	0.347118	0.932789
INT_STD	-0.128145	-0.246999	-0.073674	-0.051588	1.000000	-0.218589	-0.016685	-0.146510	-0.034853
MS_STD	0.955526	0.968763	0.784762	0.726367	-0.218589	1.000000	0.641073	0.581145	0.657430

NOB_STD	0.557833	0.754687	0.247855	0.302481	-0.016685	0.641073	1.000000	0.889521	0.047714
RES_STD	0.526519	0.683345	0.256336	0.347118	-0.146510	0.581145	0.889521	1.000000	0.041663
RESCT	0.804529	0.474468	0.974642	0.932789	-0.034853	0.657430	0.047714	0.041663	1.000000

Source: Authors computation 2026.

Exchange rate exhibits a strong positive association with GDP (0.88), current transfer (0.9), trade balance (0.86), money supply (0.95) and the interaction variable (0.80), this indicates that the variables are strongly linked with the depreciation of the Naira. However, exchange rate is weakly and positively associated with number of commercial banks branches (financial inclusion, 0.557) and reserves (0.526) suggesting that financial inclusion efforts concentrate on physical branch expansion but neglects efficient credit allocation into productive sectors of the economy whose increased output will have stabilizing effect on the Naira. Similarly, reserve is associated with a depreciating Naira, this calls for better reserve management to reduce excess import dependence and expansion of foreign exchange earning efforts into the non-oil sector in Nigeria, conversely, Exchange rate and interest rate has a weak but negative association (-0.128), this points to the fact that monetary efforts has limited stabilizing effect on the Nigerian exchange rate.

A weak positive association is noticed between reserve and the interaction term (0.04) which suggests that the interaction term is not strongly driven by reserves alone and that reserves are almost independent of the interaction term. Lastly, the association between reserve and current transfer is weak and positive (0.25), this suggests that current transfer and its management do not paly a robust role in driving reserve accumulation, in addition, current transfer is independent of reserve and will act as a good moderator in the association between reserves and exchange rate.

GMM regression results

Apart from exchange rate that is clearly endogeneous, other endogeneous variables include, current transfer, trade balance, money supply gross domestic product and the interaction variable, this is because, from economic theory, these variables also respond to changes in exchange rate These variables are specified as instruments in their lags 2 and 3 forms because lag one may still be correlated with the error term. The constant, number of bank branches and interest rates are treated as exogenous and specified in their original forms. The regression result is presented in table 4.3.

Table 4.3: GMM regression results

Dependent Variable: EXR				
Method: Generalized Method of Moments				
Sample (adjusted): 1984 2024				
Included observations: 41 after adjustments				
Linear estimation with 1 weight update				
Estimation weighting matrix: HAC (Bartlett kernel, Newey-West fixed bandwidth = 4.0000)				
Standard errors & covariance computed using estimation weighting matrix				
Instrument specification: EXR(-2) C GDP_STD(-2) IHSCT_C(-2) IHSTBL_C(-2) INT_STD MS_STD(-2) NOB_STD RES_STD(-2) RES_STD(-3) RESCT(-2)				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.

C	371.8056	162.9865	2.281205	0.0293
GDP_STD	317.3012	214.8557	1.476811	0.1495
IHSCT_C	1.36E-11	8.06E-12	1.684379	0.1018
IHSTBL_C	-1.00E-12	5.08E-12	-0.197864	0.8444
INT_STD	3.372768	11.97392	0.281676	0.7800
MS_STD	-345.1909	311.7563	-1.107246	0.2764
NOB_STD	10.16075	47.83047	0.212433	0.8331
RES_STD	-176.9671	149.0544	-1.187265	0.2439
RESCT	-9.07E-12	6.65E-12	-1.363781	0.1822
R-squared	0.979765	Mean dependent var		170.3238
Adjusted R-squared	0.974706	S.D. dependent var		252.9231
S.E. of regression	40.22519	Sum squared resid		51778.11
Durbin-Watson stat	1.182647	J-statistic		4.199332
Instrument rank	11	Prob(J-statistic)		0.122497

Source: Authors computation 2026

table 4.3 indicates that GDP has a coefficient of 371.81 with a probability of 0.1495 this means a one standard deviation increase in GDP leads to increase in exchange rate by 371.81 units but not significant, this suggests that the depreciation of the naira due to increase in GDP is not robust and can be due to chance. The inverse hyperbolic sine transformed current transfer (black tax) centered around its mean has a coefficient of 1.36E-11 with a probability of 0.1018 indicates that a one unit increase in centered current transfer is associated with an increase in exchange rate by 1.36E-11 units but also not significant. Similarly, a one standard deviation increase increase in number of commercial banks branches depreciates the naira by 10.16075 but not significant with a probability of 0.8331. in addition, a one standard deviation increase in interest rate also leads to depreciation of the naira by 3.372 units but not significant with a probability of 0.78 increases in money supply, trade balance and foreign reserve appreciates the naira. A one standard deviation increase in money supply reduces the naira exchange rate by 345.1909 but not significant, again a one unit increase in ihs centered trade balance leads to appreciation of the naira by 1.00E-12 units but the effect is not significant with a probability of 0.8444, lastly a one standard deviation increase in foreign reserves is associated with appreciation of the naira by 176.967 units but not significant.

The interaction term (resct) measures the moderating effect of black tax in the stabilization role of reserve on exchange rate. Results indicate that black tax strengthens the effect of reserve on exchange rate, an increase in black tax by one unit strengthens the stabilizing effect of foreign reserve on exchange rate by 9.07E-12 units, however this effect may be due to chance and not significant with a probability of 0.1822. increase in reserve appreciates the Naira while increase in black tax strengthens this stabilization effect, however black tax on its own has a depreciating effect on the exchange rate

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The GMM regression adopted in the study regressed exchange rate on reserves, current transfer (black tax), the interaction variable (measuring the moderating effect of black tax) and a set of control variables which include GDP, trade balance, interest rate, money supply and number of commercial bank branches that measures financial inclusion. Results indicate that increases in reserve, money supply and trade balance are associated with appreciation of the Naira, while increases in black tax, GDP, number of commercial bank branches and interest

rate are associated with depreciation of the naira. Furthermore, increase in black tax strengthens the stabilizing effect of reserve on exchange rate however this moderation effect is not significant. All the exogeneous variables are not significant at 10%. Level of significance.

Increase in reserve appreciates the naira, therefore, government policies should concentrate on further accumulation by encouraging more exports earnings from oil, expanding non-oil export earnings and maintaining prudent reserve management. Considered in isolation, increase in black tax depreciates the Naira, however as a moderator, it strengthens the appreciation of the naira through reserves, this suggests that reserve management and diaspora remittance management should be integrated and not isolated. Diaspora remittance can be encouraged through reduction in transaction cost, promotion of diaspora remittances through formal channels and the introduction of savings investment outlets like the diaspora bonds complimented by fiscal incentives. On its own, increase in black tax depreciates the naira probably because the remittances are mainly channeled into consumption, this can be corrected by encouraging investment in Small and Medium Scale enterprises and export-oriented ventures. Expanding money supply will lead to an appreciating Naira, however this could trigger inflationary pressures, the government should therefore pursue expansionary monetary policies but keep inflation in check, again, increase in trade balance appreciates the naira, this is good for economic stability, avoidance of imported inflationary pressures and improved credit rating in the international market, however, efforts must be made to ensure competitiveness of domestic products and avoid the problems of the Dutch disease. In addition, improved financial inclusion (number of commercial bank's branches) depreciates the Naira, this suggests that monetary expansion fuels factors that weaken the currency, such as, excess import demand, inefficient credit allocation and excess liquidity, therefore digital expansion rather than mere physical branch expansion, and improved supervision of the monetary efforts to elicit efficient credit allocation into productive sector of the economy should be encouraged. Lastly, increases in GDP, and interest rates associate with naira depreciation, these reveals underlying structural weaknesses in the Nigerian economy which can be revised by improving domestic production capacity, reduce import dependence and strengthen trade competitiveness.

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